

Low-Rank Multigroup Neutron Transport by Galerkin or Balanced Proper Orthogonal Decomposition

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ABSTRACT

This article presents Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) as an alternative to conventional cross section condensation. Although not always framed as such, these two techniques are analogous, except that POD assumes a low-rank rather than rank-one approximation of the solution within each coarse energy group. Starting with a fine-group neutron transport model of a 2D Watts Bar benchmark problem, we reduce cross sections by Galerkin POD, Balanced POD (BPOD), or conventional condensation. Comparing the accuracies of the resulting Reduced-Order Models (ROMs), we find that a three-group BPOD ROM can often achieve more accurate estimates of the k -eigenvalue and pin-wise fission distribution than a conventional coarse-group model with an equal or greater number of Degrees of Freedom (DoFs). Remarkably, this is despite that the conventional model assigns a particularized spectrum to each of the problem's 57,760 spatial regions (for instance, each individual pin or unit-cell of water), whereas the POD ROMs apply the same energy bases throughout. That is, BPOD enhances accuracy even while obviating the cumbersome mapping between assembly-level reference solutions and core-wide target problems required in conventional lattice physics workflows (and with it, the usual concerns about the spectral effects of core leakage or assembly interfaces).

Keywords: neutron transport, ROM, POD, BPOD, Jaguar

1. INTRODUCTION

Although ubiquitous, cross section condensation—effectively a flux-weighted averaging of fine-group cross sections into coarse groups—has two severe disadvantages: First, analysts must establish a mapping of spatial regions from reference to target problems to get acceptable results and, second, even if these problems are identical, the averaging of the fine-group spectra over each region and in angle can appreciably distort the coarse-group results. By contrast, this article demonstrates that Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) [1, 2] can be used as an analogue of conventional condensation that requires neither mapping nor averaging yet can achieve more accurate k -eigenvalues and fission rates for a given number of Degrees of Freedom (DoFs) in a 2D, quarter-core Light Water Reactor (LWR) application.

Specifically, POD accomplishes this by approximating the energy spectrum within each coarse group as a linear combination of empirical basis vectors rather than a single vector (the “weighting spectrum”) as conventionally done. This allows a POD Reduced-Order Model (ROM) to resolve variations in the fine-group spectrum, whereas a conventional coarse-group model cannot and so must apply different weighting spectra throughout the problem. As a result, POD effectively circumvents the two essential challenges of condensation above. First, there is no need to map different bases to different spatial regions, since spatial variations of the spectrum can be accounted for by varying the coefficients of the basis vectors. Second, the spectrum need not be averaged over spatial regions (collections of mesh cells) or in angle, since these coefficients vary according to the ROM's spatio-angular discretization—here, by individual mesh cells and discrete ordinates. This enables simpler yet more accurate analysis procedures than in conventional lattice physics approaches, as empirically demonstrated in Section 4.

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2. PREVIOUS WORK

Several authors have previously applied projection-based techniques, including Galerkin POD [3], to the neutron transport equation for model order reduction in energy. However, our application of Balanced POD (BPOD) [2] is novel and yields demonstrably more accurate results than Galerkin POD, at the cost of requiring adjoint (in addition to forward) reference solutions. Additionally, our empirical study of POD as a drop-in replacement for conventional condensation—that is, the reduction from fine-group to coarse-group macroscopic cross sections, given some (typically 2D, assembly-level) reference solutions—is original as well.

3. METHODOLOGY

Let us begin with the k -eigenvalue form of the neutron transport equation with L^{th} order anisotropic scattering

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}, E) + \Sigma_t(\vec{r}, E) \psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}, E) - \sum_{\ell=0}^L \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} Y_{\ell,m}(\vec{\Omega}) \int_{E_G}^{E_0} \Sigma_{s,\ell}(\vec{r}, E' \rightarrow E) \phi_{\ell,m}(\vec{r}, E') dE' \\ = \frac{1}{k} \chi(\vec{r}, E) \int_{E_G}^{E_0} \nu \Sigma_f(\vec{r}, E') \phi_{0,0}(\vec{r}, E') dE' \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where ψ is the neutron flux as a function of position $\vec{r} \in \mathcal{D}$, direction $\vec{\Omega} \in \mathcal{S}$, and energy $E \in \mathcal{G}$, in which $\mathcal{D} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ is a spatial domain, \mathcal{S} is the unit sphere, and $\mathcal{G} = [E_G, E_0)$ is the energy scale. Further, $Y_{\ell,m}$ are real spherical harmonics and $\phi_{\ell,m}$ are spherical harmonic moments of ψ . Finally, the remaining terms are the total cross section Σ_t , the scattering cross section(s) $\Sigma_{s,\ell}$, the emission spectrum χ , and the fission neutron production cross section $\nu \Sigma_f$. In practice, the spatial and energy dependencies of these terms are assumed to be separable such as in

$$\Sigma_t(\vec{r}, E) = \sum_c N_c(\vec{r}) \sigma_{t,c}(E) \quad (2)$$

(and likewise for $\Sigma_{s,\ell}$ and $\chi \nu \Sigma_f$) where N_c is either the number density of nuclide c or an indicator function of material c depending on whether the cross sections $\sigma_{t,c}$, $\sigma_{s,\ell,c}$, χ_c , and $\nu \sigma_{f,c}$ are microscopic or macroscopic.

3.1. Low-Rank Multigroup Transport

The multigroup discretization first entails partitioning the energy scale \mathcal{G} into groups $\mathcal{G}_g = [E_g, E_{g-1})$. Next, within each group, the flux ψ is approximated as rank- R_g (in a conventional, vice low-rank, multigroup discretization, $R_g = 1$) separable in energy

$$\psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}, E \in \mathcal{G}_g) \approx \sum_{j=1}^{R_g} \psi_{g,j}(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) v_{g,j}(E) \quad (3)$$

where $v_{g,j}$ are trial functions and $\psi_{g,j}$ are the corresponding spatio-angular components. To obtain the low-rank multigroup model, one then operates on Equation 1 by $\langle w_{g,i}, \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{G}_g}$ with test functions $\{w_{g,i}\}_{i=1}^{R_g}$ (in the conventional rank-one case, the sole test function is unity, $w_{g,1} = 1$) where $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{G}_g}$ denotes an inner product such as

$$\langle w_{g,i}(E), v_{g,j}(E) \rangle_{\mathcal{G}_g} = \int_{E_g}^{E_{g-1}} w_{g,i}(E) v_{g,j}(E) dE. \quad (4)$$

Additionally, let $w_{g,i}$ and $v_{g,j}$ be biorthogonal such that Equation 4 equals the Kronecker delta δ_{ij} and as a consequence

$$\psi_{g,i}(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) \approx \left\langle w_{g,i}(E), \psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}, E) \right\rangle_{\mathcal{G}_g}. \quad (5)$$

Given these preliminaries, let us aggregate the components of the flux into column vector $\psi_g = [\psi_{g,1} \cdots \psi_{g,R_g}]^\top$ and likewise $\phi_{g,\ell,m}$. Then, the semi-discrete low-rank neutron transport equation in group g can be written

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \psi_g(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) + \Sigma_{t,g}(\vec{r}) \psi_g(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) - \sum_{\ell=0}^L \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} Y_{\ell,m}(\vec{\Omega}) \sum_{g'=1}^G \Sigma_{s,\ell,g' \rightarrow g}(\vec{r}) \phi_{g',\ell,m}(\vec{r}) \\ = \frac{1}{k} \chi_g(\vec{r}) \sum_{g'=1}^G \nu \Sigma_{f,g'}(\vec{r}) \phi_{g',0,0}(\vec{r}) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where the cross sections remain separable in space and energy, like in Equation 2, with the entries of the nuclide- or material-wise cross section matrices $\sigma_{t,g,c} \in \mathbb{R}^{R_g \times R_g}$, $\sigma_{s,\ell,g' \rightarrow g,c} \in \mathbb{R}^{R_g \times R_{g'}}$, $\chi_{g,c} \in \mathbb{R}^{R_g \times 1}$, and $\nu \sigma_{f,g',c} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times R_{g'}}$ being integrals of their continuous-energy (or at least, finer-group) counterparts

$$\sigma_{t,g,c,i,j} = \left\langle w_{g,i}(E), \sigma_{t,c}(E) v_{g,j}(E) \right\rangle_{\mathcal{G}_g} \quad (7a)$$

$$\sigma_{s,\ell,g' \rightarrow g,c,i,j} = \left\langle w_{g,i}(E), \int_{E_{g'}}^{E_{g'-1}} \sigma_{s,\ell,c}(E' \rightarrow E) v_{g',j}(E') dE' \right\rangle_{\mathcal{G}_g} \quad (7b)$$

$$\nu \sigma_{f,g',c,j} = \int_{E_{g'}}^{E_{g'-1}} \nu \sigma_{f,c}(E') v_{g',j}(E') dE' \quad (7c)$$

$$\chi_{g,c,i} = \left\langle w_{g,i}(E), \chi_c(E) \right\rangle_{\mathcal{G}_g}. \quad (7d)$$

Despite the perhaps unfamiliar presentation, the above is in fact a generalization of the conventional rank-one multigroup discretization, in which $R_g = 1$ and $w_{g,1} = 1$, with the non-essential caveat that $v_{g,j}$ is here the same for all $\vec{r} \in \mathcal{D}$ rather than particularized to each material subdomain \mathcal{D}_c (as in, that indicated by N_c). That is, the conventional rank-one approximation sets

$$v_{g,1}^{(c)}(E) = \frac{\int_{\mathcal{D}'_c} \phi(\vec{r}, E) dr}{\int_{E_g}^{E_{g-1}} \int_{\mathcal{D}'_c} \phi(\vec{r}, E) dr dE} \quad (8)$$

where ϕ is the reference scalar flux and \mathcal{D}'_c is the subdomain of the reference problem corresponding to \mathcal{D}_c . Having said that, some derivations include nuances that contradict Equation 3, such as transport corrections, but these are beyond the scope of our discussion.

3.2. Proper Orthogonal Decomposition

Given the low-rank multigroup model of Equation 6, it remains only to define the test and trial functions $w_{g,i}$ and $v_{g,j}$. These could be any biorthogonal functions but, as in conventional condensation, we here extract them from a set of rank-one fine-group reference solutions. However, while the conventional approach would be to average the solution (over \mathcal{D}_c and \mathcal{S}), let us instead extract basis vectors from the Gramians of the solution(s) by POD.

To elaborate, for a single (rank-one) G -group solution ψ , the forward Gramian $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{G \times G}$ is comprised of values

$$X_{g,g'} = \langle \psi_g, \psi_{g'} \rangle_{\mathcal{D} \times \mathcal{S}} \quad (9)$$

where $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{D} \times \mathcal{S}}$ is a spatio-angular inner product as in

$$\langle \psi_g, \psi_{g'} \rangle_{\mathcal{D} \times \mathcal{S}} = \int_{\mathcal{D}} \int_{\mathcal{S}} \psi_g(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) \psi_{g'}(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) d\Omega dr. \quad (10)$$

For multiple reference solutions, \mathbf{X} is just the (possibly weighted) sum of the Gramian for each individual solution, but to avoid cluttering the notation we do not detail that case here.

In practice, since the solutions are here computed numerically by a discrete ordinates (S_N) method in angle and the Slice Balance Approach (SBA) in space, these inner products are approximated as

$$X_{g,g'} \approx \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_K \Delta\Omega_n \psi_{g,n,K} V_K \psi_{g',n,K} \quad (11)$$

where $\Delta\Omega_n$ is the quadrature weight, V_K is the cell volume, and $\psi_{g,n,K}$ is the cell-average flux for each ordinate n , cell K , and group g . Note that this formulation makes clear that $X_{g,g'}$ can be computed without storing the entire multigroup angular flux vector ψ in memory simultaneously (which would typically be memory prohibitive). Rather, upon convergence, $\psi_{g,n}$ can be recomputed and stored for all groups g simultaneously but only one ordinate n at a time.

Finally, since POD is applied in each coarse group individually, the following sections detail only the degenerate case of a single coarse group (the index of which is omitted) for convenience. In short, the objective is, given forward Gramian \mathbf{X} (and, for BPOD, the adjoint Gramian \mathbf{Y}), to compute the test and trial matrices $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{G \times R} = [\mathbf{w}_1 \cdots \mathbf{w}_R]$ and likewise \mathbf{V} whose columns \mathbf{w}_i and \mathbf{v}_j are the multigroup representations of functions w_i and v_j . Let us begin with the Galerkin POD, where $w_i = v_i$.

3.2.1. Galerkin Proper Orthogonal Decomposition

Although Galerkin POD requires that the test and trial bases to be equal, the choice of inner product is arbitrary. Let us take the inner product in energy to be that defined by

$$\mathbf{M}_{\mathcal{G}} = \text{diag}(\Delta u_1^{-1}, \dots, \Delta u_G^{-1}) \quad (12)$$

as in $\langle \mathbf{w}_i, \mathbf{v}_j \rangle_{\mathcal{G}} = \mathbf{w}_i^T \mathbf{M}_{\mathcal{G}} \mathbf{v}_j$ where $\Delta u_g = \ln(E_{g-1}/E_g)$ is the lethargy width of group g . This weighting can be incorporated into the test basis $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{M}_{\mathcal{G}} \mathbf{V}$. That is, a Galerkin projection in an inner product space with $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{G}}$ can be cast as a Petrov–Galerkin projection in the Euclidean vector space.

Given this, it remains only to compute a trial basis \mathbf{V} which is orthogonal in $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{G}}$, such that $\mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{M}_{\mathcal{G}} \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{I}$. This is accomplished by computing the eigendecomposition

$$\widehat{\mathbf{X}} = \widehat{\mathbf{W}} \Lambda \widehat{\mathbf{W}}^T \quad (13)$$

where $\widehat{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{L}_{\mathcal{G}}^T \mathbf{X} \mathbf{L}_{\mathcal{G}}$ is the weighted Gramian given Cholesky factorization $\mathbf{M}_{\mathcal{G}} = \mathbf{L}_{\mathcal{G}} \mathbf{L}_{\mathcal{G}}^T$. Note that since $\mathbf{M}_{\mathcal{G}}$ is here diagonal, $\mathbf{L}_{\mathcal{G}} = \mathbf{L}_{\mathcal{G}}^T = \mathbf{M}_{\mathcal{G}}^{1/2}$ is the square root of $\mathbf{M}_{\mathcal{G}}$. Given $\widehat{\mathbf{W}}$, the test and trial bases can be obtained as

$$\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{L}_{\mathcal{G}} \widehat{\mathbf{W}} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{L}_{\mathcal{G}}^{-T} \widehat{\mathbf{W}} \quad (14)$$

from which it is clear that $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{M}_{\mathcal{G}} \mathbf{V}$ and so $\mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{M}_{\mathcal{G}} \mathbf{V} = \widehat{\mathbf{W}}^T \widehat{\mathbf{W}} = \mathbf{I}$. Of course, other choices of $\mathbf{M}_{\mathcal{G}}$ are possible, including \mathbf{I} , in which case $\widehat{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{X}$ and $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{V} = \widehat{\mathbf{W}}$. Given \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{V} , the Galerkin ROM is achieved by truncating these bases to the desired rank R .

3.2.2. Balanced Proper Orthogonal Decomposition

While the Galerkin POD, as above, effectively seeks the best low-rank approximation of the reference solution(s) in what amounts to an L^2 norm, this may not be the best choice of norm as it does not account for the model's sensitivity to a given feature. That is to say, the features of the solution that are large in the L^2 norm are not necessarily those which drive a model's response (for example, contribute most to the fission source), and vice versa.

This sensitivity can be quantified by the adjoint flux distribution ψ^\dagger . Given a corresponding adjoint solution, let us define the adjoint Gramian $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{G \times G}$ with values

$$Y_{g,g'} = \left\langle \psi_g^\dagger, \psi_{g'}^\dagger \right\rangle_{\mathcal{D} \times \mathcal{S}}. \quad (15)$$

Following Laub et al.'s balancing transformation [4], we begin by Cholesky factorizing the forward and adjoint Gramians as $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{L}_X \mathbf{L}_X^\top$ and $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{L}_Y \mathbf{L}_Y^\top$. Then, computing the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) of the product

$$\mathbf{L}_Y^\top \mathbf{L}_X = \widehat{\mathbf{W}} \mathbf{S} \widehat{\mathbf{V}}^\top \quad (16)$$

the test and trial bases are obtained as

$$\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{L}_Y \widehat{\mathbf{W}} \mathbf{S}^{-1/2} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{L}_X \widehat{\mathbf{V}} \mathbf{S}^{-1/2} \quad (17)$$

and can then be truncated to the desired rank R . Note that, despite appearances, the BPOD can in fact be interpreted as a Galerkin POD in the inner product space induced by \mathbf{Y} (that is, redefining $\mathbf{M}_G = \mathbf{Y}$ in Section 3.2.1), apart from the normalization of the bases [2].

4. NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS

To evaluate the effectiveness of Galerkin and Balanced POD as compared to conventional condensation, let us consider a 2D version of the Watts Bar Unit 1, Hot Zero Power (HZP) problem defined in the VERA benchmark suite [5] at Beginning of Life (BOL). Specifically, beginning with a fine-group (SHEM-361 [6]) reference solution—the pin-wise fission distribution of which is plotted in Figure 1—we generate conventional cross sections in 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 12, 14, 16, 23, 25, 40, and 70 groups. These coarse-group structures are determined by rounding the CASMO breakpoints to the nearest breakpoints in lethargy of the SHEM-361 structure. As usual, each of the model's 57,760 spatial regions (for instance, each individual pin, tube, and unit-cell of water) is assigned a particularized fine-group spectrum. Notably, unlike in a practical lattice physics workflow, there is no difference between the reference and target problems besides cross section condensation—that is, we aim solely to reproduce the reference solution.

Figure 1. Pin-wise fission distribution from the fine-group reference solution; model parameters.

Figure 2. Forward (per unit lethargy squared) and adjoint fine-group Gramians of the angular flux.

Meanwhile for POD, given the Gramians plotted in Figure 2, we generate biorthogonal energy bases in 3 coarse groups, with interior breakpoints at roughly 0.625 eV and 5 keV, near those of the CASMO-4 mesh (omitting the 0.821 MeV breakpoint), which divide the energy scale into thermal, intermediate, and fast ranges. The first four modes of the resulting Galerkin and balanced energy bases are shown in Figure 3. To compute the cross section matrices, these bases are truncated to some rank R_g in each coarse group; these thresholds can (and in practice, should) be set individually for each group, but for simplicity we here set them all equal, $R_g = R$, where $R = 2, 4, \dots, 20$. To reiterate, unlike in the conventional case, both energy bases \mathbf{W}_g and \mathbf{V}_g are spatially independent (that is, they are not particularized to material subdomains \mathcal{D}_c).

Having executed each ROM, let us examine the absolute error of k -eigenvalues, $|k - k_{\text{fine}}|$, and the Relative Root Mean Square Error (RRMSE) of the fission rates F_p in each fuel pin p with volume V_p

$$\sum_p V_p (F_p - F_p^{\text{fine}})^2 / \sum_p V_p (F_p^{\text{fine}})^2 \quad (18)$$

versus the fine-group eigenvalue k_{fine} and fission rates F_p^{fine} , as illustrated in Figure 4. Doing so, we first find that BPOD achieves far more accurate answers than Galerkin POD at a given number of DoFs—often by roughly a factor of five or more in k -eigenvalue and one to three orders-of-magnitude in fission rate RRMSE. Likewise, compared to the conventional coarse-group model, the BPOD model is more accurate by all metrics except the k -eigenvalue error at $R = 2$. In fact, beyond 12 DoFs, the BPOD ROM often achieves k -eigenvalue errors and fission rate RRMSEs that are one to four orders-of-magnitude less than those of the conventional model.

To investigate further, the spatial distribution of pin fission errors (again relative to the fine-group solution) for the conventional and BPOD ROMs is plotted in Figure 5. From this, one finds that the conventional model incurs a persistent bias towards the core periphery and away from the interior, ranging from roughly $\pm 4\%$ at 7 groups to $\pm 0.3\%$ at 70 groups. On the other hand, the BPOD errors appear closely associated with the assembly loading pattern—for instance, up through $R = 8$ one largely sees an overprediction in the 3.1% enriched assemblies and an underprediction in the 2.11% enriched assemblies (with the 2.619% enriched assemblies somewhere in between). These errors start at about $\pm 6\%$ with $R = 2$ —though the most extreme relative errors are only in the low power pins at the edge of the core—and decrease by about an order-of-magnitude or more with each doubling of R . As such, for $R \geq 4$, the BPOD ROM is more accurate than the conventional model as judged by the maximum absolute relative error in pin fission for a given number of DoFs.

Figure 3. Energy bases from Galerkin and Balanced POD and (lower right) decay of eigenvalues λ_i and singular values σ_i relative to λ_1 and σ_1 respectively.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we have developed a means of cross section condensation based on either Galerkin or Balanced POD as opposed to simply averaging the flux. Evaluating each ROM empirically in a 2D Watts Bar benchmark, we find that a 3-group BPOD ROM (for ranks $R \geq 4$) is consistently able to achieve k -eigenvalue errors and pin-wise fission RRMSEs less than those of a conventional coarse-group model with an equal or greater number of DoFs. Remarkably, this is despite that, whereas the conventional model assigns a particularized spectrum to each of the problem's 57,760 distinct spatial regions, the POD ROMs apply the same energy bases throughout. That is, BPOD obviates the cumbersome mapping of spatial regions between reference and target problems (and with it, the usual concerns about core leakage and environment effects) even while enhancing accuracy in k -eigenvalue and fission rate estimates.

Figure 4. Error of k -eigenvalue and fission rate estimates from each ROM relative to fine-group reference solution.

Figure 5. Pin fission rate errors relative to fine-group reference solution, as incurred by BPOD and conventional condensation; note the different scales.

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